

artigo

Lógica, tecnologia e criatividade

1 de 17 70%

Abstract

The clearest dimension on the presence and participation of the designer in society starts with changing social, economic, cultural, and technological transformations involved in a conception of the world with specific features and requirements, but that can vary according to the culture, society and the economy. It is establishing context to the public the need to plan for social policies and proposals. Essentially, these days, as steps of an individual's life, and one of several processes that are part of social reality. Thus, studying the creativity in their methods of conducting by techniques used is that get along a logic to the contemporary reality of society through applied social sciences in the study design. With new technologies, experience stimulates creative projects. With creativity, the design has importance for its productive diversity. Either individually or with the foundations in society, are accomplishments that may be how useful.